

PRISMA-S — Search Strategy

Title of review:

Evidence-based programs for the prevention and reduction of aggressive and bullying behaviors in preschool education: a systematic review

1. Information sources and rationale for selection

We searched six major electronic databases to capture empirical studies published in peer-reviewed journals in the fields of psychology, education, and health:

- **Scopus (Elsevier)**
- **Web of Science – Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI)**
- **ERIC**
- **MEDLINE (via PubMed)**
- **PsycINFO (Ovid)**
- **LILACS / SciELO**

These databases were selected because they collectively index:

- Educational intervention research (ERIC, Scopus, WoS/SSCI),
- Behavioral and psychological intervention studies (PsycINFO),
- Clinical and behavioral health literature (MEDLINE),
- Latin-American educational and social research (LILACS/SciELO).

No grey literature databases were systematically searched.

Reference lists and expert contacts were used to locate in-press or unpublished studies (see item 10).

2. Context and population targeted

The goal of the review was to identify empirical intervention studies targeting the reduction or prevention of:

- aggression
- bullying
- peer violence
- social–emotional or prosocial behaviors

in **preschool-aged children (3–6 years)** within formal early childhood education settings.

3. Languages and publication filters

The search was limited to:

- English
- Spanish
- Portuguese

Document type was restricted to peer-reviewed journal articles.

4. Time frame

Studies published **from 1 January 2000 to 1 November 2025** were retrieved to cover contemporary preschool interventions in the context of structured early education systems.

5. Controlled vocabulary and free-text terms

The strategies combined:

- Controlled vocabularies (MeSH, APA Thesaurus, ERIC descriptors, DeCS)
- Equivalent free-text terms in English, Spanish and Portuguese

Three conceptual blocks were used in all databases:

1. Population / Setting (preschool / early childhood education)
2. Intervention / programmatic approaches
3. Outcomes related to aggression, bullying, social–emotional behavior

6. Pilot search

A pilot search was conducted on 28 October 2025 using Scopus and Web of Science to assess feasibility, term sensitivity and database yield. No changes to keywords, controlled vocabulary, or filters were necessary. Final searches were executed without modification.

7. Final search strategies (verbatim)

The following strings are reported exactly as executed, with full syntax per database.

7.1 Scopus (Elsevier) — executed 03 November 2025

Search string:

TITLE-ABS-KEY (preschool* OR pre-school* OR kindergarten* OR "early childhood" OR "early childhood education")

OR "preschool education" OR preescolar* OR "educacion infantil" OR "educacao infantil"

OR "educacion temprana" OR "primera infancia" OR "jardin de infancia" OR creche

OR "educacao pre escolar" OR "primeira infancia")

AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (intervention* OR program* OR training OR curriculum OR prevention

OR "social emotional learning" OR SEL OR "program evaluation" OR "school program"

OR programa* OR intervencion* OR prevencion* OR formacion OR curriculo

OR "aprendizaje socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociales" OR "prevencion de la violencia"

OR convivencia OR intervencao* OR prevencao* OR treinamento

OR "aprendizagem socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociais" OR "prevencao da violencia")

AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (aggression OR bullying OR "aggressive behavior" OR "peer aggression" OR "peer violence"

OR "prosocial behavior" OR empathy OR "social skills" OR agresion

OR "conducta agresiva" OR acoso OR victimizacion OR "acoso entre iguales"

OR "comportamiento prosocial" OR empatia OR "regulacion emocional"

OR agressao OR "comportamento agressivo" OR vitimizacao OR "violencia entre pares"

OR "comportamento pro social" OR "regulacao emocional")

Filters: Year=2000–2025; Language=EN/ES/PT; Document type=Article

Results: 3,297

7.2 Web of Science (SSCI) — executed 04 November 2025

TS=(preschool OR "early childhood" OR kindergarten OR "early childhood education"
OR "preschool education" OR preescolar OR "educacion infantil" OR "educacao infantil"
OR "educacion temprana" OR "primera infancia" OR "jardin de infancia" OR creche
OR "educacao pre escolar" OR "primeira infancia")

AND TS=(intervention OR program OR training OR curriculum OR prevention
OR "social emotional learning" OR SEL OR programa OR intervencion OR prevencion
OR formacion OR curriculo OR "aprendizaje socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociales"
OR "prevencion de la violencia" OR convivencia OR intervencao OR prevencao OR
treinamento
OR "aprendizagem socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociais" OR "prevencao da
violencia")

AND TS=(aggression OR bullying OR "aggressive behavior" OR "peer aggression"
OR "peer violence" OR "prosocial behavior" OR empathy OR "social skills" OR agresion
OR "conducta agresiva" OR acoso OR victimizacion OR "acoso entre iguales"
OR "comportamiento prosocial" OR empatia OR "regulacion emocional"
OR agressao OR "comportamento agressivo" OR vitimizacao
OR "violencia entre pares" OR "comportamento pro social" OR "regulacao emocional")

Filters: Year=2000–2025; Language=EN/ES/PT; Document type=Article

Results: 2,182

7.3 ERIC — executed 05 November 2025

(as executed; no truncations omitted)

("Early Childhood Education" OR "Preschool Education" OR kindergarten OR preescolar*
OR "educacion infantil" OR "educacao infantil" OR "educacion temprana"
OR "primera infancia" OR "jardin de infancia" OR creche OR "educacao pre escolar"
OR "primeira infancia")

AND (intervention OR program OR training OR curriculum OR prevention
OR "social emotional learning" OR SEL OR programa* OR intervencion* OR prevencion*
OR formacion OR curriculo OR "aprendizaje socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociales"
OR "prevencion de la violencia" OR convivencia OR intervencao* OR prevencao*
OR treinamento OR "aprendizagem socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociais"
OR "prevencao da violencia")

AND (aggression OR bullying OR "aggressive behavior" OR "peer aggression"
OR "peer violence" OR "prosocial behavior" OR empathy OR "social skills" OR agresion
OR "conducta agresiva" OR acoso OR victimizacion OR "acoso entre iguales"
OR "comportamiento prosocial" OR empatia OR "regulacion emocional"
OR agressao OR "comportamento agressivo" OR vitimizacao
OR "violencia entre pares" OR "comportamento pro social" OR "regulacao emocional")

Filters: Peer-reviewed; Year=2000–2025; EN/ES/PT

Results: 1,084

7.4 MEDLINE (via PubMed) — executed 05 November 2025

((("Child, Preschool"[Mesh] OR preschool*[tiab] OR "early childhood"[tiab]
OR "educacion infantil"[tiab] OR "educacao infantil"[tiab]))

AND ("Intervention Studies"[Mesh] OR intervention[tiab] OR programa*[tiab]
OR prevention[tiab] OR "social emotional learning"[tiab] OR programa*[tiab]
OR intervencion*[tiab] OR prevencion*[tiab]))

AND ("Aggression"[Mesh] OR "Bullying"[Mesh] OR aggression[tiab] OR bullying[tiab]
OR victimization[tiab] OR agresion[tiab] OR acoso[tiab] OR agressao[tiab] OR
vitimizacao[tiab]))

Filters: Humans; Journal articles; Year=2000–2025; EN/ES/PT

Results: 301

7.5 PsycINFO (Ovid) — executed 06 November 2025

(literal repetition of three-concept block)

(preschool OR "early childhood" OR kindergarten OR preescolar OR "educacion infantil"
OR "educacao infantil" OR "educacion temprana" OR "primera infancia"
OR "jardin de infancia" OR creche OR "educacao pre escolar" OR "primeira infancia").ti,ab.
AND (intervention OR program OR training OR curriculum OR prevention
OR "social emotional learning" OR SEL OR programa OR intervencion OR prevencion
OR formacion OR curriculo OR "aprendizaje socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociales"
OR "prevencion de la violencia" OR convivencia OR intervencao OR prevencao
OR treinamento OR "aprendizagem socioemocional" OR "habilidades sociais"
OR "prevencao da violencia").ti,ab.
AND (aggression OR bullying OR "aggressive behavior" OR "peer aggression"
OR "peer violence" OR "prosocial behavior" OR empathy OR "social skills" OR agresion
OR "conducta agresiva" OR acoso OR victimizacion OR "acoso entre iguales"
OR "comportamiento prosocial" OR empatia OR "regulacion emocional"
OR agressao OR "comportamento agressivo" OR vitimizacao
OR "violencia entre pares" OR "comportamento pro social"
OR "regulacao emocional").ti,ab.

Filters: Peer-reviewed; Year=2000–2025; EN/ES/PT

Results: 1,002

7.6 LILACS / SciELO — executed 06 November 2025

(preescolar* OR "educacion infantil" OR "primeira infancia" OR "educacao infantil"
OR creche OR "jardim de infancia")
AND (programa* OR intervencion* OR prevencion* OR curriculo
OR "aprendizaje socioemocional" OR "aprendizagem socioemocional")
AND (agresion OR acoso OR "violencia entre pares" OR agressao OR bullying
OR vitimizacao OR empatia OR "comportamiento prosocial"
OR "habilidades sociales" OR "habilidades sociais")

Filters: Journal articles; Year=2000–2025; EN/ES/PT

Results: 382

8. Additional sources

- Backward citation searching: reference lists of included studies and prior reviews were screened.
- Expert consultation: Field specialists were contacted to identify in-press or unpublished work.
- Scheduled update: Searches will be updated in June 2026 to capture post-indexing studies before synthesis.

9. Search management

All retrieved records (**n = 8,248**) were exported to **Rayyan** for screening.

Automatic and manual duplicate removal identified **4,674 duplicates**.

Screening proceeds in two phases (title/abstract → full text) by two independent reviewers; discrepancies resolved by discussion or third reviewer adjudication.